

SPORTSMAN SPIRIT AND QUALITIES OF A TRUE SPORTSMAN

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Sportsman spirit doesn't mean only taking part in sports and playing the game in conformity with the rules prescribed, but also playing the game of life in the spirit imbibed on the playing fields. A man who gives evidence of possessing a sporting spirit in games is still a sportsman. Sportsmanship is, in a basic sense, conforming to the rules of sport. It may also be considered as the will to go out & win fairly or lose gracefully. Sportsmanship expresses an aspiration or ethos that the activity will be enjoyed for its own sake, with proper consideration for fairness, ethics, respect, and a sense of fellowship with one's competitors. Some people define good sportsmanship as the "golden rule" of sports in other words.

To spell success in any sports four's' are required; skill ,stamina , style and sportsman spirit. To demonstrate good sportsmanship first we should have respect for ourself, teammates, opponents, coaches on both sides, referees, Judges and other officials.

Sportsmanship typically is regarded as a component of morality in sport, composed of three fair play, sportsman spirit, and character. Fair play refers to all participants having an equitable chance to pursue victory and acting toward others in an honest, straightforward, and a firm and dignified manner even when others do not play fairly. Character refers to dispositions, values and habits that determine the way that person normally responds to desires, fears, challenges, opportunities, failures and successes and is typically seen in polite behaviors toward others such as helping an opponent up or shaking hands after a match.

Facets of sportsmanship have been identified as a player's full commitment to participation respect and concern for rules and officials, respect and concern for social conventions avoiding poor attitudes toward participation.

But sportsmanship isn't just reserved for the people on the field. Cheerleaders, fans, and parents also need to be aware of how they behave during competition. Sportsmanship is a style and an attitude, and it can have a positive influence on everyone. Good sportsmanship takes maturity and courage when we work really hard at a sport. If someone continues taunting you or your team after the competition is over. Sometimes it's hard to swallow. Our pride and walk on. But there's always the next match. When we lose don't take it out on your

opponent, blame the officials, or blame your team. Take it in stride. When we lose, lose with class. Being proud of how we performed, or at least being aware of things. We need to improve for next time, is key. Good sportsman spirit means congratulating the winners promptly and willingly. Also, it means accepting the game's outcome without complaint and without excuses. Good sportsman spirit means acknowledging victories without humiliating opponents, being quietly proud of success, and letting victories speak for themselves. Even if we win by a landslide, good sportsmanship means still finding ways to compliment We should try to learn as much as we can about the sport. Play by its rules. Show up for practice, work hard, and realize that on a team, everyone deserves a chance to play.

Good sportsman spirit doesn't allow players to respond with violence. A true sportsperson cheers his teammates on with positive statements, avoids trash-talking the other team, acknowledges and applauds good plays, even when someone on the other team makes them, personally checks on a player in case of an injury and is mature enough to know that sometimes, in sports, it's not that your team lost - it's just that the other team won. When officials make a call, accept it gracefully even if it goes against you. Remember that referees may not be right every time but they're people who are doing their best, just as you are. Whether we win or lose, congratulate your opponents on a game well played.

Good sportsmanship means not having a "win at any cost" attitude. Most athletes who don't have a "win at any cost" attitude are more likely to talk about how much they love their sport and how much personal satisfaction and enjoyment they get from participation. To Triumph in a competition against ones equals in any field is a euphoric feeling. In the arena of sports more than in any other field, this sense of euphoria is most visible, demonstrative and spontaneous. Nations take great pride in the glory of their sportspersons; their achievements are equated with the honor of the nation. Riches and privileges are heaped on those who climb the summit of success in their chosen field. The incentives given and the expectations placed on the sportspersons are so immense that the sportspersons are under tremendous pressure to succeed at all costs. In a competition with other individuals with almost the same skills, talent and abilities, there is no guarantee that success will be yours only. In such a scenario, it is not uncommon for some sportsperson to use unfair means to lob off that fraction of a second or jump that extra cm to get ahead of the field. The practice of using performance enhancing drugs in all the major sports disciplines continues unabated despite all the preventive measures put in place by the authorities running these sports. Lifetime bans, fines and the consequent sense of shame, has not acted as deterrent. Such is the desperation to win at all cost. In the face of such an attitude, qualities like sportsman spirit, appreciation and

